

EFFECTIVE WEB DESIGN STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING MEDIA TECHNOLOGY COMPETENCE

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Annotation: This article defines the concepts of media competence and web design, providing examples from the information on the topic supported by scientists' opinions. Despite partially covering the work of scientists, it is based on specific facts. The article discusses the connections between media competence and media culture, characteristics of people with media competence, strategies used to develop media competence among students, the three main concepts of web design, and lists the stages of web design.

Keywords: media literacy, media competence, media culture, web design, mass media, web technology, web site, web page, web server, teacher, student.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the development of modern information and communication technologies (ICT), the concept of media competence is becoming increasingly relevant. In the current era of globalization, the concept of media competence is one of the new terms and encompasses a wide range of media information (transmission, evaluation, learning, ability to convey). Web design plays an important role in this process, since the effective creation and use of Internet resources contribute to the development of media literacy.

Media competence is an integral quality, types, forms, and genres, manifested in the ability of students to select media texts in various conditions, use them, critically analyze and evaluate information, be ready to create and transmit news, analyze the complex processes of the activities of mass media in the life of society.

Media competence is a multifaceted concept and operates in several areas:

- knowledge;
- methods of activity;
- expresses personal characteristics.

Media competence, media literacy, and media culture are closely related concepts and can be used synonymously. The teacher, possessing media competence, that is, the powers of the press, its causes, knowledge, skills, and abilities, should teach students knowledge related to media education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A.B. Fedorov, in order to form media culture in media education, considers creative, communicative potential, creative thinking, critical thinking as a process of personal development using mass media and materials for the purpose of teaching various forms of self-expression using media techniques, full perception, interpretation, analysis and evaluation of media texts.

A person who has mastered a certain direction of media competence is a person who has formed knowledge and skills worthy of their field, capable of creative thinking and effective actions. From this, we can learn that the sum of the mutual qualities of a person's knowledge,

skills, and abilities within the framework of certain disciplines and actions is the acquisition of competence corresponding to a person's actions.

People with media competence have the following characteristics:

- the desire to obtain new information;
- striving for the world of media culture;
- search for the necessary scientific materials;
- constant communication with media products;
- having the ability to independently generate and disseminate media texts;
- ability to freely work with media-related sources.

The media competence of a teacher is aimed at spiritual, motivational, intellectual, and practical self-development, volitional and emotional self-management.

A specialist with media competence can consistently enrich their knowledge, assimilate new information, deeply understand the requirements of the time, search for new knowledge, process it, and effectively apply it in their practical activities. According to Zemek, there is no clear and unique agreement on what to do with competence. The concept of media competence can first be found in Deter Baacker's dissertation "Communication and Competence." As a result of such research, it can be concluded that media competence is the active use of all types of mass media for the repertoire of communication and action.

Swan and Biderman commented on media competence as follows: media competence allows students to determine the reliability of sources and, together with making informed decisions, encourages evidence-based practices.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to Kohtala, media competence develops creativity and innovative thinking, allowing students to effectively use media tools to solve problems and communicate. According to Lanham, media competence encourages digital citizenship and teaches students to be responsible and ethical in online communities.

Strategies used in the development of media competence among students:

- gaining practical experience in the effective use of various media and technologies, creating opportunities for conducting classes;
- stimulating critical thinking and analyzing media reports;
- training in the recognition and assessment of the ethical consequences of using mass media.

Every person who uses media must have the necessary skills to critically evaluate and analyze a message in today's age, which is bombarded with various messages. Without proper guidance and education on media literacy, media platforms may remain vulnerable to the threat of manipulation by advertising, social media, and media. According to Rill and Childress, the ability to use media platforms not only strengthens cooperation and engagement among media users but also prepares them to use technology more in the workplace.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to Mifsud and Barthollet, the adiacative concept in digital actions is well equipped to solve problems related to the authenticity of human privacy and intellectual property rights. In a general sense, media competence is a set of basic skills for people

entering the professional sphere, equipping them with the necessary tools for development in a world saturated with mass media.

One of the serious impacts of social networks on students' media competence is the erosion of critical thinking skills. Too much information makes it difficult to distinguish between what is true and what is not. There may be cases of detecting the falsity or authenticity of information and a critical attitude towards its use, accepting inaccurate or misleading information, and not suspecting the information. The weakness or absence of a person's ability to critically evaluate leads to a misunderstanding of the world and information and can hinder analytical thinking. At the same time, the most important role in the development of media competence of people, especially the younger generation, is played by their parents and guardians.

The concept of web design and its essence:

Web design is the process of developing internet resources. In this process, areas such as graphic design, programming, user interface (UI), and user experience (UX) design are used in an integrated manner. Modern web projects require a high level of interactivity, functionality, and aesthetics.

The 3 basic concepts of web design are:

1. A web page is a document that has its own unique address and can be viewed using a browser.
2. A web server is a computer or program connected to a network. Serves to provide or manage shared resources to the client.
3. A website is a logical combination of many web pages.

The stages of web design are:

Stage 1. Data collection: Defining the goal and target audience.

Stage 2. Design. Selection of programming languages for creating a website map and marketplace.

Stage 3. Design. Create templates, compare them, get reviews from clients, and make changes when necessary.

Stage 4. Create content. Content writing and preparation for transfer.

Stage 5. Deployment and development. Creating, improving the site, adding interactive elements. SEO optimization.

Stage 6. Testing and launch. Website testing, uploading to the server, final testing, and launching.

Stage 7. Support. Adding reviews to the system, troubleshooting errors, updating the site.

Just as creating a website doesn't begin with writing code, it doesn't end after the site is launched. The initial stage influences the subsequent stages. At the same time, it determines the effectiveness of the project work.

The role of web design in the formation of media competence:

1. Information Analysis and Filtering - In the process of web design, users develop skills in identifying reliable and high-quality information sources.

2. Increasing digital literacy - knowledge and skills in the creation and use of Internet resources increase the level of media literacy.

3. Creation of an interactive educational environment - creation of interactive educational platforms through web projects in the educational process, development of students' ability for independent research and analysis.

CONCLUSIONS AND PROPOSALS

In conclusion, we can say that in the current era of globalization, media competence and web design are considered modern concepts, and we know that it is a requirement of the developing era that every person should have information about these two concepts not only in the educational process, but also in other processes. The process of web design is the result of methods of forming media competence. People with high media competence have an increased interest in web design and can create their own project, understanding the sequence of stages. The theoretical foundations of web design, in particular, through the use of Web 2.0 technologies, are an integral part of the formation of media competence. These tools allow learning in collaborative and competency-based learning, which is necessary for the development of important media skills in the learning environment.

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